

Implicit Upper-Limb Prosthesis Control from Compensatory Body Motions

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Abstract—Notwithstanding recent progress in the control of prosthetic limbs, the independent control of a multiplicity of joints, such as in pluriarticulated proximal upper-limb amputations, remains complex and tiresome to users. As an alternative or an addition to classical myoelectric control, few studies have indicated the possibility of measuring compensatory motions of residual limbs of users for controlling their prostheses. In this paper, we introduce an algorithm that generalizes this idea, allows to interpret residual limb motions as encoding the user’s intention of motion, and translate it into prosthesis control to achieve a desired reaching task. We validate this approach in simulation for a transhumeral subject, and experimentally demonstrating the control of a 5-DoF robotic arm via human motions tracked by Inertial Measurement Units (IMUs) sensors.

Index Terms—Upper-limb Prosthetic Control, Compensatory Motions

I. INTRODUCTION

Many people with limb loss (due to e.g. neurological disorders, accidents, and infections [1]) find robotic prostheses a crucial assistance to continue performing their daily activities. However, too complex control systems often lead to passive use of even the most advanced prostheses, and their eventual rejection [2]. Dominant among techniques used today to control active prostheses are myo-electric interfaces, which detect the muscular activity from the stump residual muscles to command the prosthetic degrees of freedom (DoFs) [3]. Usually, two electromyography (EMG) sensors are required to control each Degree of Freedom (DoF) [4]. EMG control is very effective and stable. However, it has limitations that become apparent when the level of amputation is more proximal, since more EMG measurements are required, while fewer residual muscles are available [5].

Some control strategies resort to mapping temporal or spatial input patterns onto a finite number of control modes. However, learning the patterns or training a net can be too difficult and tiresome for users [6], [7]. It is well known [8] that, when one or more DOFs in a prosthetic system are missing or unreliably operated, people tend to compensate for function with other bodily DOFs.

The introduced *compensatory motions* tend to be unnatural and straining, yielding discomfort, pain, and on the long period chronic postural problems [9]. The magnitude of compensatory motions has often been considered as an inverse metric to evaluate the quality of prosthetic systems [10], [11]. Based on

this observation, Legrand et al. present the idea of using compensatory motions as an input for the upper-limb prosthetic control.

In [12], M. Legrand introduced a theoretical framework, which relies on a kinematic description of the prosthetic wearer and correlates the outputs of prosthetic joint velocities to the user’s compensation behavior. She proposed two different approaches to measure the compensation: the first one is based on the direct measurement of human joints, while the second on the position and orientation of the prosthesis base body. This last method is the one she developed and presented in [13], [14], by testing it for one and two prosthetic DoFs with real subjects.

In this paper, we extend the first theoretical approach, by considering the possibility of the compensatory behavior being influenced not only by human joints but also by prosthetic joints. We extend the paradigm to more complex prostheses, by considering the relationship between prosthesis control and the compensatory motions performed by the user as if it were a dynamic system to control. We validate the proposed approach both in simulations and in experiments with up to 5 DoFs to be controlled.

II. PROBLEM DEFINITION

Consider the differential kinematics of a person using a prosthesis

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{e}_e \\ \dot{e}_c \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\bar{x}}_e \\ \dot{\bar{x}}_c \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} \dot{x}_e \\ \dot{x}_c \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\bar{x}}_e \\ \dot{\bar{x}}_c \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} J_{he}(q) & J_{re}(q) \\ J_{hc}(q) & J_{rc}(q) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{q}_h \\ \dot{q}_r \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where:

e_e is the reaching error between the goal position \bar{x}_e of the hand frame and its actual position x_e , e_c is the compensation error between the shoulder’s rest position \bar{x}_c and its actual value x_c , $J_{he}(q)$, $J_{re}(q)$, $J_{hc}(q)$, and $J_{rc}(q)$ are the human and prosthetic Jacobian matrices, that are functions of the joint coordinates $q = [q_h^T, q_r^T]^T$, organized in q_h - for the human joints, and q_r - for the robotic prosthesis joints.

Consider \dot{q}_h and \dot{q}_r as the main inputs of the system. The first one is controlled by the human, the second one by the prosthesis. Our goal is to define a control law for the prosthetic joints that applied to the system (1) together with the unknown action of the user stabilizes both errors to zero. Since the target frame \bar{x}_e is known only by the user, the definition of such a control law is not trivial, and has to be in the form $\dot{q}_r = \Gamma_r(q, \bar{x}_c)$.

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Fig. 1. Simulated trans-humeral amputee in a reaching task: with a passive prosthesis (top row) and with the proposed control (bottom row). Target frame x_e (red dot) on the right hand, compensatory frame x_c on the shoulder (blue dot). Photo-sequence @ $t = [0, 0.2, 0.5, 1, 2, 10]$ secs. The position of \bar{x}_e (yellow dot) is $[0.3, -0.2, 0.2]$ meters. \bar{x}_c is displayed by the blue color in transparency.

III. TECHNICAL APPROACH

O1: Prosthetic users are usually able to use compensation to move the target frame x_e toward the desired configuration for \bar{x}_e even though the prosthetic joints are not operated [8].

A consequence of **O1** is that when $\dot{q}_r = 0$ one gets

$$\dot{e}_e|_{\dot{q}_r=0} = J_{he}\dot{q}_h = \Gamma_h(e_e, e_c, q_h, q_r), \quad (2)$$

where $\Gamma_h(e_e)$ is the control action of the human, which is function of all the variables, is such that $e_e \rightarrow 0$.

Assume now that the robot controller introduces a small perturbation δx_{er} in the position of the target frame. Again by virtue of **O1**, the human operator will always achieve equilibrium of the target frame compensating

$$\delta x_{eh} = -\delta x_{er}, \quad (3)$$

with an equal and opposite variation of the target frame induced by motions of q_h . We assume the kinematic equivalent of a virtual short [15] and extend (3) to yield $J_{he}\dot{q}_h \approx -J_{re}\dot{q}_r$.

As consequence of **O1**, a generalized inverse J_{he}^\dagger of J_{he} always exists. Therefore we assume that the human joint motion has the form

$$\dot{q}_h = -J_{he}^\dagger \dot{x}_{er} + N_{he}\lambda_h, \quad (4)$$

where the $N_{he}\lambda_h$ are a base of the null space of J_{he} and λ_h are motions in such null space generated by the human. In this study, we neglect the effects of the null-space for simplicity. If we substitute (4) in the second of (1) and by considering the effect of the robotic joints to the compensation as $\dot{x}_{cr} = J_{rc}\dot{q}_r$ we get

$$\dot{x}_c = J_{hc}\dot{q}_h + J_{rc}\dot{q}_r = -J_{hc}J_{he}^\dagger \dot{x}_{er} + \dot{x}_{cr}. \quad (5)$$

In order for the prosthesis controller to reduce the compensatory action required from the human, we drive the robotic action given by \dot{x}_{er} and \dot{x}_{cr} as close as possible to a term proportional to the compensation error. Assuming that J_{hc} is full row rank, we obtain that

$$\dot{x}_{er} - (J_{hc}J_{he}^\dagger)^\dagger \dot{x}_{cr} = -(J_{hc}J_{he}^\dagger)^\dagger k_c e_c. \quad (6)$$

Finally, inverting for \dot{q}_r yields the proposed controller

$$\dot{q}_r = -(J_{re} - (J_{hc}J_{he}^\dagger)^\dagger J_{rc})^\dagger (J_{hc}J_{he}^\dagger)^\dagger k_c e_c, \quad (7)$$

When no robotic joints take part in the compensation, and therefore $J_{rc} = 0$, we simplify (7) into

$$\dot{q}_r = -J_{re}^\dagger (J_{hc}J_{he}^\dagger)^\dagger k_c e_c. \quad (8)$$

Note that the simplified controller (8) is similar to what proposed in [12] that is

$$\dot{q}_r = \lambda(-J_{hc}J_{he}^\dagger J_{re})^\dagger e_c, \quad (9)$$

that had a similar approach of mapping e_c in \dot{q}_r (λ is a gain). However, we explicitly map the compensation error into a cartesian motion \dot{x}_{er} first, then proceed to map this in a robot motion \dot{q}_r . Where our approach and [12] correspond were all matrices square and invertible, since it is not true in general that $(AB)^\dagger = B^\dagger A^\dagger$, the two solutions do not match always in practice, and behave differently in the proximity of singularities, as we show numerically in the next session.

IV. RESULTS

In Fig. 1, we present a Matlab/Simulink simulation of a trans-humeral amputee donning a four DoFs prosthesis (elbow and the wrist), comparing the performance when using a

Fig. 2. Sequence of frames for a simulated prosthesis user with the prosthetic controller turned on. \bar{x}_e is set outside user's workspace at $[0.6, -0.3, 0.2]$ meters. The corresponding reaching and compensation errors are also reported.

passive prosthesis - first row vs. when using the proposed controller (8) - second row. The compensatory target frame is placed on the user's right shoulder (blue dot), and therefore the compensatory behavior is influenced only by human joints ($J_{rc} = 0$). Where the task error e_e is minimized in both cases, only when the prosthetic controller is turned on we see the shoulder goes back to the rest position, therefore minimizing the compensation error.

It is now also interesting to consider a third example, with \bar{x}_e outside the user's workspace, as shown in Fig. 2. The prosthetic arm is now fully extended to minimize the reaching error. Although this is not enough to reach \bar{x}_e , and consequently the user still continues to compensate without fully canceling the compensation error, we can still appreciate (i) the stability of the control loop and (ii) the fact that the compensation error is still reduced with respect to what it would be if using a passive prosthesis in the same configuration. The corresponding plot of the errors for this task can be seen in Fig. 3.

We can consider then an additional task, which requires more complex prosthesis motion. We set in the reaching target a desired orientation, different from the one the subject normally has at the rest position. We see how also for this task, the user performs compensatory motions, and the controller understands human intentions, leading the prosthetic hand to the desired target frame. A sequence of frames for this task is reported in Fig. 4 and the corresponding errors in Fig. 3.

As mentioned in the previous section, we carried out an empirical analysis to observe the behavior of our controller in comparison to the one theoretically described in [12]. We consider the case of the desired reaching target placed outside the user's workspace, as the case reported in Fig. 2. We run the same simulation 20 times, with all gains set to one. Each simulation runs twice, one by implementing controller of [12] reported in (9), and one with our control law of (8). We set 20 different reaching poses and we run the simulation until the reaching of a steady state configuration, or, if not reached, for a maximum duration of 50 seconds. By comparing the reaching errors at the steady state configurations, we have empirically demonstrated that our controller effectively enables the user to achieve the desired pose, better than the state-of-the-art controller. The left side of Fig. 3 illustrates the errors for our controller for a specific pose, while the errors for the state-of-the-art controller are presented in Fig. 5. In Fig. 5, we also depict representations of all 20 reaching target poses (denoted

by red dots) that we considered. The green dot represents the world frame (user's pelvis), while the blue dot the starting pose of user's hand. Nevertheless, it is important to note that our analysis was primarily empirical, and while it provides valuable insights, further research is essential to assess the most optimal operational conditions for each controller.

V. EXPERIMENTS

We validate the proposed approach with two experiments. The first experiment represents a virtual twin of the user wearing a trans-humeral prosthesis. In the second experiment the motions of the user up to the shoulder are mapped on a robotic avatar, whereas the robot avatar is controlled with

Fig. 3. Reaching and compensation errors when the reaching target is outside user's workspace (left) and when a different desired hand orientation is set (right).

Fig. 4. Sequence of frames for a simulated prosthesis user with the prosthetic controller turned on. \bar{x}_e is set at $[0.3, -0.3, 0.4]$ meters for the linear component and at $[0.1, 0.04, 1.66]$ radians for the orientation component.

the proposed algorithm as it were a prosthesis. For both experiments, the compensatory target frame is placed on the user's right shoulder and no influence of the robotic joints to the compensatory behavior is considered ($J_{rc} = 0$). We

implement both experiments within Robot Operating System (ROS) Noetic framework and use MVN XSens 2021.2 for tracking upper-body human motions. Additional details of the experiments can arise from the video in attachment.

Experiment 1: The subject, while looking at their virtual twin reported in Fig. 6, wants to move the virtual prosthetic arm so that the hand frame reaches the green bottle (the yellow dot in the virtual world). The user compensatory motions x_c correspond to them bending the trunk and moving forward the right shoulder.

Experiment 2: In this experiment, we use a robotic arm attached to the two-wheeled avatar AlterEgo (Fig. 7) as prosthesis. To match the bodies of the human and of the robot, we map the user shoulder frame x_c to the avatar wheels as in $\dot{x}_w = k(x_c - x_w)$ (where k is a suitable gain) so to keep the user's and avatar's shoulders aligned. Then, we implement the controller (8), taking care of using, in the definition of J_{re} , J_{he} , the kinematic of the robot arm (which constitutes the prosthetic part of the system).

Fig. 5. Reaching and compensation errors when the reaching target is outside user's workspace (left) for the state-of-the-art controller [12]. On the right side, representation of the 20 reaching targets (red dots) with respect to the user's pelvis frame (green dot) and the starting pose of user's hand (blue dot). For the state-of-the-art vs our approach, the mean of the linear reaching error is 0.0424 m and $2.1765e-04\text{ m}$, the mean of the linear compensation error is 0.3906 m and 0.2329 m , and the mean of the orientation reaching error is 0.0730 rad and 0.0005 rad . The standard deviation of the state-of-the-art vs our approach for the linear reaching error is 0.1008 m and $6.3149e-04\text{ m}$, for the linear compensation error 0.1292 m and 0.0877 m , while for the orientation reaching error is 0.2696 rad and 0.0014 rad .

VI. MAIN EXPERIMENTAL INSIGHTS

Experimental results (in Fig. 6 for Experiment 1 and in Figs. 7 and 8 for Experiment 2) show the reaching and compensation errors converge to zero. It is worth noticing how the algorithm has been successfully applied to two UL prostheses with different DoFs (4 in Experiment 1, 5 in Experiment 2). This suggests potential applications of the method to practical cases.

Task completion time is still roughly one order of magnitude larger than what a user would require without a prosthesis. Feedback from the user performing the experiments so far highlight that it is easier to control the end-effector position along some direction rather than others. Moreover, orientation control sometimes feels bulky. We suspect those issues may relate to those directions along which some of the jacobians tend to become ill-conditioned, and to the intrinsic incomparability between angles and lengths. We expect to improve over this aspect with finer tuning of the controller gains, and by calibrating the weight matrices in the pseudo-inverses. Moreover, in experiments we observed some difficulty in keeping the prosthesis still on the desired configuration, since even the smallest displacement of the user's shoulder still generates motions of the prosthesis. We expect to target this kind of issues with the introduction of some form of non-linear gains and/or with some dead-band about \bar{x}_c .

Fig. 6. Experiment 1 photo-sequence. The target is the yellow dot ($\bar{x}_e = [0.40, 0.0, 0.250]$ meters with respect to human pelvis).

Fig. 8. Reaching position and compensation errors during task execution.

From the experiments, we see how as the user compensates, the prosthesis starts to move. The control loop is closed by the human, that as soon as s/he is satisfied with the achieved end-effector pose goes back to their target position, leading the prosthetic arm to stop. Therefore, since it is human behavior which triggers the controller, we never give the same input to the loop. Consequently, no measure over the repeatability and accuracy can be assessed, unless the human inputs would be recorded, and played back. The prosthetic controller when active must be able to understand human's intentions, and by generating prosthetic motion outputs proportional to the compensatory behavior, must lead the user to correct their posture, going back to their rest configuration. We highlight as important features of this controller the possibility to decrease the reaching error, to control more DoFs simultaneously, and the reduction of compensatory motions. For what concerns the possibility to decrease the completion time, a better tuning of controller gains is necessary.

In future studies, we plan to replicate the study including multiple subjects (able-bodied first, and amputees after) using real prosthetic arms, and to compare the proposed controller to the other state-of-the-art approaches. Expected performance metrics will include usability, task completion time, peak and residual task error, and peak and residual compensatory error. Moreover, we plan to extend the approach to control different prostheses, including lower limbs, exoskeletons, and avatars, also thanks to the consideration of J_{rc} in our control loop. The application of such extension would include the field of the assistive robotics, in particular for supporting the rehabilitation of people with limited motion possibilities, affected e.g. by stroke, multiple sclerosis, or spinal cord injuries.

Fig. 7. Experiment 2 photo-sequence. Motions (compensatory) of the user and corresponding robotic arm motions. Target pose is the green bottle ($\bar{x}_e = [0.35, -0.15, 0.5]$ meters with respect to human pelvis). The red lines highlight the wheel's displacement.

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